

THE HISTORY OF TRANSLATION

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Abstract. This article delves into the complex history of translation, tracing its origins and evolution through various historical periods. Translation is defined as the process of transferring text from one language to another, with its roots in Latin and ancient Greek. The history of translation is categorized into four major periods: from BC to the 3rd century AD, from the 5th to the 15th century AD, from the Renaissance to World War II, and from post-World War II to the present day.

Key words: *translation, translator, texts, inscriptions, transferring, history.*

The process of translation is complicated in its own way, it is an activity of transferring the source from the original language - the target language to another language - the target language, and translation is its result. The word "translation" is derived from Latin and means "to bring" or "to carry". According to other sources, this word comes from the ancient Greek word "metaphrasis" (metaphrase) and it means to speak in tongues or to translate word for word. Translation studies, like other sciences, goes back to ancient times. When talking about its history, first of all, the bilingual Assyrian and Mesopotamian inscriptions, the Rosette inscriptions of Ancient Egypt, and the texts translated from Greek in Ancient Rome come to mind.

Historically, the Sumerian epic "Gilgamesh" is indicated as the source of the first translation, but in fact, the history of translation goes back to the time when people appeared on earth and tribes were formed. According to many scholars, the first translators were the hunters of that time[2]. They encountered a stranger while hunting, and were required to study and interpret the sounds he made in order to obtain information about his abode, an early form of the translation process. So, at first, the translation was created in oral form.

The history of translation in the West and East includes three periods[1;1721-1723]:

1. Translation activity from BC to the third century AD. This period includes all translations made in ancient times. For example, texts translated from Hebrew into ancient Greek.

2. The period from the fifth to the fifteenth century AD. Many books were translated into Latin, Greek and Arabic.

3. The period from the Renaissance and the modern era to the Second World War.

We considered it appropriate to add the fourth period, i.e., the period after the Second World War to the present day, to the above periodization type. As an example of this period, it is possible to show the modern translation version of Abdulla Qadiri's work "O'tkan kunlar" called "Bygone days".

Historically, the earliest translation source is the Sumerian epic of Ancient Mesopotamia, Gilgamesh. This saga has been translated into Asian languages. Another ancient example of translation is the inscriptions on the Rosetta Stone. The inscriptions on this stone are written in two languages - hieroglyphic and demotic, and it was translated into ancient Greek. There is information that Buddhist monks in ancient China translated Indian texts into Chinese[1].

Later, in Ancient Rome, various Greek texts were translated, especially Greek sources were translated and harmonized into Latin. Similar sources belong to Cicero and Horace in Rome, and their translated works were used until the 17th century. In addition, the works of Greek scholars were translated by Arab scholars, and this process caused these works to spread around the world. After the Arabs conquered the Greeks, they translated the scientific works available there and formed their own scientific works based on these works. Later, these translated works were again translated into Latin. In addition, the Arabs translated many works. In particular, VIII - IX, they also translated Sanskrit texts into their own language.

In England, translation studies began in the 9th century. During the reign of King Alfred, the process of translating Latin works into English began. During the reign of Queen Elizabeth, translation studies was divided into two parts:

1. The period from the reign of King Henry VIII to the 17th century.
2. The period from the 17th century to the present day.

In the early period, translation studies appeared in England related to the process of translating religious books. The first translator in the history of England was J. Shosse, who translated religious books called "Bible" and "Ramount of Rose" into English. The Irish scholar T. Shelton translated the works of "Don Quixote" and "Homer", J. Dryden the works of Virgil, A. Pop Homer's works "Iliad" and "Odyssey". During the Victorian period, the field of translation studies was further developed. In particular, Maurica and White together translated the oldest epic called "Beawulf". Fitzgerald translated Omar Khayyam's works, Benjamin Plato's Republic.

The next period of English translation studies began in the 20th century, in which A. Vailey translated Chinese works. "John and Cross" was translated during this period.

After the conquest of the Turanian land by the Arabs, Islamic culture spread widely in this area. In particular, science, literature, history, theology, philosophy, and medicine developed during this period. Many of our scholars went to Egypt, Syria, Iraq, Iran, and Byzantium to study. The works of our scientists such as M.M. Khorazmi, Ibn Sina, I. Beruni, Termizi, N. Kubro, A. Yassavi began to be translated into Latin in the 12th century. It is known that in the East, translation was done freely and through interpretation[6.7.8.]. Many works were translated at the Ma'mun Academy through this method. When Caliph Harun al-Rashid marched to Byzantium, he brought many books from there to Baghdad and ordered them to be translated into Arabic.

This article explores the evolution of translation across different historical periods. It defines translation as the process of transferring text from one language to another, tracing its etymology to Latin and Greek roots. The history of translation is divided into four periods[4]:

1. From BC to the 3rd century AD: This period includes ancient translations such as texts translated from Hebrew to Greek and the Sumerian epic "Gilgamesh."

2.5th to 15th century AD: This era saw many works translated into Latin, Greek, and Arabic.

3. Renaissance to XXII: Marked by significant translation activities, particularly from Greek to Latin and other languages.

4. Post-XXII to present: Modern translations, exemplified by works like "Bygone Days" by Abdulla Qadiri.

Significant early examples of translation include the Rosetta Stone inscriptions and the translation of Indian texts by Buddhist monks in China. The document highlights the translation activities in Ancient Rome and later in England, noting key figures and works translated. It also mentions the spread of Islamic culture and the translation efforts in the Islamic world, particularly through institutions like the Ma'mun Academy.

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